

**Effects of people-centred factors on enterprise resource planning implementation
project success: Empirical evidence from Sri Lanka**

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Abstract

Extant literature suggests people-centred factors as one of the major areas influencing enterprise resource planning (ERP) implementation project success. Yet, to date, few empirical studies attempted to validate the link between people-centred factors and ERP implementation project success. The purpose of this study is to empirically identify people-centred factors that are critical to ERP implementation projects in Sri Lanka. The study develops and empirically validates a framework for people-centred factors that influence the success of ERP implementation projects. Survey research methodology was used and collected data from 74 ERP implementation projects in Sri Lanka. The people-centred factors of “project team competence”, “rewards”, and “communication and change” were found to predict significantly the ERP implementation project success.

Key words: enterprise resource planning; ERP implementation; human resource.

1. Introduction

The application of computer-based information systems has steadily developed over the past several decades following, and motivating, advances in scientific and administrative technology. An ERP system represents the latest and most ambitious application of administrative and computer-based technologies in the management information systems. It enables a firm to gain a holistic view of the business enterprise: it promises one database, one application, and a unified interface across the entire enterprise (Bingi *et al.* 1999). Many firms implement ERP packages as a means to reduce operating costs, enhance competitiveness, increase productivity and improve customer services (see Davenport 1998, Jang *et al.* 2009, Mabert *et al.* 2003).

However, the implementation of the system is difficult and places tremendous demands on corporate time and resources (Al-Mashari 2002, Al-Mashari *et al.* 2003). Many ERP implementations have been classified as failures because they did not achieve predetermined corporate goals (see Umble *et al.* 2003, Zhang *et al.* 2005).

Though often-reported problems during or after ERP implementation are easily blamed on complex technology ERP implementation is a “triple play” that combines people, technology, and processes (see Yusuf *et al.* 2004). Yet, to date, a few empirical studies attempted to validate the link between people-centred factors and ERP implementation project success (e.g. Arnold 2006, Sun *et al.* 2009). Therefore, enquiries and understanding must extend beyond the technical aspects of ERP implementation (see Arnold 2006, Morton and Hu, 2008, Dillard and Yuthas 2006, Turnipseed *et al.* 1992). This paper attempts to empirically identify people-centred factors that are critical to the success of ERP implementation projects in an Asian developing country, Sri Lanka. For the study, quantitative research methodology was used and collected data from 74 ERP implementation projects in Sri Lanka.

Further, research on enterprise information systems (EIS) has primarily examined the experiences of specific organizations that implemented EIS, detailing a single case study of how they implemented the system in their organization (e.g. Bingi *et al.* 1999, Chien and Tsaur, 2007, Koh *et al.* 2000, Mandal and Gunasekaran 2002, Motwani *et al.* 2002, Snider *et al.*, 2009, Wilson *et al.* 1994, Yusuf *et al.* 2004). While case studies provide insights into the impact of EIS in specific situations, the lack of generalisability has hampered the development of theory or an overarching framework for interpreting and framing research applicable across organisations (Arnold 2006). Hence, the need of rethinking the methodologies that are being applied in contemporary EIS research has been emphasized (see Arnold 2006). However, it should be noted that some researchers conducted large scale surveys to investigate ERP system “adoption” by collecting data mainly from employees of the firms that have implemented packaged software (e.g., Katerattanakul *et al.*, 2006; Mabert *et al.* 2000; Olhager and Selldin 2003). However, our study is different from these surveys as the objective of our study is to investigate people-centred factors that are critical in the ERP system implementation process from ERP implementation project team

members' perspective. As detailed in section 3.2, data was collected from project team members engaged in 74 ERP implementation projects in Sri Lanka.

Furthermore, literature on ERP or EIS originates from and describes application contexts in North America, Western Europe as well as countries in the Asia-Pacific region such as Australia, China, Hong Kong, and Taiwan, where most ERP developers are located and implementations have occurred. Anecdotal information suggests that countries all over the world tend to identify ERP as one of the widely accepted choices to obtain competitive advantage. Extant literature suggests that valuable lessons could be learned from implementation experiences in different parts of the world (see Avison and Malaurent, 2007, Davison 2002, Sheu *et al.*, 2004, Soh *et al.* 2000). In response to several factors, such as increasing global competition, lower labour costs in Sri Lanka and inducements from the Sri Lankan government, the number of international businesses coming into the country has been increasing since the introduction of open economic policies in 1977. In the context of globalisation of business operations and interlocking supply chains, a research on ERP systems in South Asia (Sri Lanka in particular) is interesting, relevant and timely since relatively little is known about ERP implementations in this part of the world. For instance, our review of journals that are outlets for information systems related research in popular databases of Business Source Premier, ABI/Inform, Emerald, ScienceDirect, and Wiley Blackwell has been unable to find any studies conducted on enterprise systems in less developed countries, not even in India. The extent to which the research findings on ERP implementation contexts in North America, Western Europe as well as countries in the Asia-Pacific region could be generalized to the South Asian context has not been widely tested. Therefore, the research setting is both progressive and international in nature as the paper explores a timely issue while maintaining an international perspective of the Sri Lankan context situated in a global environment. From a practical standpoint, we believe that the findings of this exploratory study will be able to provide practitioners with key information that could

enable them to make informed managerial decisions in a country that is considered an active and promising destination for investment in the Asian region. On the other, the findings of this exploratory study will be able to establish baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Consistent with the objectives, the rest of the paper reviews briefly the theoretical background of the study. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The paper concludes with a discussion on managerial implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

2. Theoretical background

2.1. ERP implementation project success

Most organisations realise the potential of ERP systems, yet struggle to materialise real benefits. The specific literature on ERP systems suggests that ERP implementation project success is different from traditional information system success measures in that it is not evaluated by end-users but by the project team members (see Hong and Kim 2002). Implementation project success is frequently defined in terms of the achievement of some predetermined goals, which normally include multiple parameters such as clarity (Delone and McLean 2003), accuracy (Wu and Wang 2007), timelines (Bailey and Pearson 1983, Wu and Wang 2007), content (Delone and McLean 1992, 2003), system stability (Wu and Wang 2007), flexibility (Bailey and Pearson 1983), reliability (Wu and Wang 2007, Yusuf *et al.* 2004), project is completed within time and budget (Al-Mashari *et al.* 2003, Hong and Kim 2002, Kumar *et al.* 2003, Lyytinen and Hirschheim 1987), and the achievement of the business case (Hong and Kim 2002). Appendix A summarises ERP implementation project success measures mentioned in literature. However, most studies that measured ERP implementation project success used only one or two surrogates of

ERP implementation project success (e.g. Ang *et al.* 1994, Burns and Turnipseed 1991, Mabert *et al.* 2003, Umble *et al.* 2003, Wilson *et al.* 1994, Zhang *et al.* 2005).

2.2. People-centred factors that influence ERP implementation projects

Extant literature on ERP implementation projects identifies “people” as a major factor in detecting the performance of an ERP implementation project in an enterprise (e.g. May and Kettelhut 1996, Sun *et al.* 2005). Researchers (e.g. Sumner 1999, Holland and Light 1999) have listed people issues in their critical success factors recommendations when dealing with ERP implementation projects. In addition, many researchers (e.g. Evans 1994, Marjanovic 2000, Wang, 2007, Zucchi and Edwards 1999) state that a major reason for failure of business process re-engineering is the lack of attention towards people-centred issues. Hence, people must get the highest priority when it comes to ERP implementations (see Koh *et al.*, 2008, Loh and Koh 2004, Sun *et al.* 2005, Turnipseed *et al.* 1992, Yoon, 2009) and human resource should be used in an appropriate manner for the successful ERP implementations (see Hawa *et al.* 2002, May and Kettelhut 1996). Appendix B summarises people-centred factors influencing ERP implementation projects mentioned in literature.

Some of the main people-centred factors that influence successful ERP implementations are composition of the project team, organizational roles and structures, communication, and compensation (refer to Appendix B). Due to its complexity and scope, ERP implementation projects are handled by implementation teams composed of top-notch people who are chosen for their skills, past accomplishments, reputation, and flexibility. These people are entrusted with critical decision making responsibility (Umble *et al.* 2003). Evidence shows that lack of expertise in terms of development capabilities, application-specific knowledge, and user experience contributes to project risk (see Keil *et al.* 1998, Sumner 2000, Umble *et al.* 2003). Hence, having the right composition of the ERP implementation project team is identified as very important (see Bingi *et al.* 1999, Nah *et al.* 2001, Umble *et al.*

2003, Woo 2007). Further, extant literature identifies the roles of the project team members and the allocation of responsibility to them as critical elements in ERP implementation projects (e.g. Hawa *et al.* 2002, Kraemmerand *et al.* 2003, Umble *et al.* 2003, Wang *et al.* 2005). Furthermore, literature suggests that if the system implementation is not tied to compensation, it will not be successful. When teams reach their assigned goals, rewards should be presented in a very visible way (Umble *et al.* 2003). Moreover, an ERP implementation is predominantly a change management project (Kraemmerand *et al.* 2003, Teltumbde 2000). Effective communication between groups has been identified as a significant factor in enhancing co-operation and reducing resistance to change (see Al-Mashari *et al.* 2003, Wang and Chen 2006) whilst its absence has been proposed as a risk factor in EIS implementations (see Markus *et al.* 2000, Sumner 2000, Umble *et al.* 2003, Ward *et al.* 2005).

Though extant literature suggests people-centred factors that influence ERP implementations (see Sun *et al.* 2005), it is very scarce to find empirical studies that investigated a range of people-centred factors and their influence on ERP implementations. Therefore, relatively little is known about the impact of people-centred factors on ERP implementation projects. Given the empirical and anecdotal evidence that indicate association between people-centred factors and ERP implementation project success (refer to Appendix A and B), for this Sri Lankan study, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive significant association between people-centred factors and ERP system implementation project success.

3. Research methods

3.1. Measures

The variables used in the study could be broadly classified into two, i.e., ERP implementation project success (dependent variable) and people-centred factors of ERP system implementation (independent variables). The scope of the study is limited to ERP implementation issues after the purchase of the ERP hardware and software. Although one could argue that ERP implementation is a never-ending cycle of continuous improvement, the focus of this study is on initial implementation efforts, and the immediate success results achieved from those efforts (e.g. Sun *et al.* 2005).

Multiple-item Likert-type scales were used to measure both sets of variables. The measures for ERP implementation project success were developed based on the previously reviewed related literature (refer to Appendix A). The measures for people-centred factors of ERP system implementation were also developed based on the previously reviewed relevant literature (refer to Appendix B). For the purpose of the study, both sets of variables were defined broadly. Sample measures used are: “Accuracy of the system: data accuracy (no change of data) between the business processes”; “Clarity of the system: information provided by the system conveys the intended meaning”; “Stability of the system: data robustness (no loss of data) between the business processes”. As detailed in section 3.2, respondents of the survey were persons who have been involved in an ERP implementation project as a project-team member. Hence, project-team members’ awareness of the meanings of ERP system implementation project success measures and people-centred issues was considered as an advantage. Where available, scale items from existing research were used. For the constructs that did not have readily available scale items, appropriate scale items were developed using guidelines recommended by Nunnally (1978). In doing so, first, the domain of the relevant construct was specified. Then, items were developed to map the construct’s conceptual definition, and finally, the items were pre-tested on a convenience sample of 10 implementation project team members that fit with the intended sample of the study and revised accordingly. The resultant list consisted of 7-item ERP implementation project success measure and 16-item people-centred

aspects measure. These two measures are given in Appendix C. All the measures were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1= very low to 5= very high.

3.2. Sample and data collection

The list of firms that implemented ERP systems was obtained from a firm that conducted a comprehensive market survey on ERP systems in use in Sri Lanka. The list contained 90 firms belong to the private sector operating in Sri Lanka. The objective of our study is to investigate the people-centred factors that are critical in the implementation process of ERP systems. The specific literature on ERP system implementation success suggests that ERP implementation success is different from traditional information system success measure in that it should be evaluated by the project team members (see Hong and Kim 2002). Hence, our study examined people-centred factors that impact ERP system implementation from project team members' perspective.

Data was collected from one of the randomly selected main persons who have been involved in the ERP implementation project as a project-team member in each firm. For this 90 contact persons were identified from each firm. Contact persons were instructed to distribute the link to the on-line survey to a randomly selected ERP system implementation project team member via e-mail. At the beginning of the questionnaire, instructions of filling the survey was provided along with the purpose of the research and ensured confidentiality. Although 82 records were saved on the database from the on-line link, eight records were considered incomplete and had to be discarded. This left 74 valid responses, a response rate of 82 per cent of the original sample. When considering the education level of the respondents, all the respondents have either Bachelors degree or a postgraduate degree as the highest level of education. The profile of the firms and respondents are shown in Table 1.

Take in Table 1

3.3. Data analysis procedure

The data was analysed in several phases. Internal consistency (standardised Cronbach's alpha) of the scale was examined to ensure the measures were unidimensional. Inter-item correlation analysis was conducted for ERP implementation project success measure and measure for people-centred factors. Principal-components factor analysis was conducted. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test statistics were calculated. Confirmatory factor analysis was conducted using AMOS 16 for each of the construct separately to assess convergent validity (see Blunch 2008).

4. Exploratory analysis

4.1. Item analysis

The summary statistics of people-centred aspects and ERP implementation project success variables are shown in Appendix D.

Prior to conducting principle component factor analysis, internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha) was examined to ensure measures were unidimensional. Results showed that 7-item ERP implementation project success measure had a reliability of 0.798 and 16-item people-centred aspects measure had a reliability of 0.938 (refer to Appendix C). The ratio between the number of respondents and the number of variables in the model well satisfied the set criteria (2:1) for successful factor analysis (Kline, 1994).

4.2. Principle component factor analysis

Principle component factor analysis was used to validate the dimensions (see Blunch 2008). In order to derive a stable factor structure the criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (see Hair *et al.* 1998). For ERP implementation project success measure, factor analysis yielded one factor and explained 67.3 per cent of the variance (refer to Table 2). With regard to people-centred aspects measure, five iterations yielded a set of three factors, which explained 80.9 per cent of the variance (refer to Table 2). Again the ratio between the number of respondents and the number of extracted factors in the independent variable well satisfied the set criteria (20:1) for successful factor analysis (Kline, 1994). These three factors were labelled as “Project team competence”, “Rewards”, and “Communication and change”.

Confirmatory factor analysis was conducted for each of the construct separately to assess convergent validity (Blunch 2008). AMOS 16.0 was used. Table 2 shows the summarised results of reliability analysis (standardised Cronbach's alpha), principle component factor analysis (explained variation and eigenvalue) and confirmatory factor analysis (standardised regression estimates and associated p-values) of ERP implementation project success and three components of people-centred factors.

Take in Table 2

Table 3 shows descriptive statistics and zero-order correlations among study variables. As can be seen from Table 3, three components of people-centred factors have positive significant association with ERP system implementation project success.

Take in Table 3

5. Model-data fit

Fit measures relating to absolute fit (CMIN/df, GFI), relative fit (CFI), parsimonious fit (PRATIO), and fit measures based on the non-central chi-square distribution (RMSEA, PCLOSE) were used to evaluate the model-data fit (see Arbuckle 2007, Blunch 2008). Table 4 shows the fit measures for the model. The model well satisfies the requirements of goodness-of-fit criteria (see Arbuckle 2007, Blunch 2008, Byrne 2001). Figure 1 shows final research model with regression weights. The coefficient of determination (squared multiple correlation) of .698 suggests that project team competence, rewards, and communication and change account for 70 per cent of the variation of ERP implementation success in the final model. The data fails to reject the hypothesis that the three components of people-centred factors significantly related to ERP system implementation project success.

Take in Table 3

Take in Figure 1

6. Discussion and concluding remarks

Whilst it is recognised that people-centred factors are critical for ERP implementations, few empirical studies attempted to validate the link between people-centred factors and ERP system implementation project success. Hence, ERP system implementation literature provides little guidance on people-centred factors that

contribute to the success or responsible for failure of ERP system implementation projects. This research attempted to empirically identify some of the people-centred factors that are critical to the implementation of ERP systems. Therefore, this article represents a progress toward the development of a measure of people-centred factors in ERP system implementation project success.

We have used widely accepted multiple parameters drawn from literature (refer to Appendix A) to evaluate ERP implementation project success. The 7-item measure used in this study was empirically based and was shown to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context. Similarly, we have drawn item measures to evaluate people-centred factors that influence ERP implementation project success from the extant literature (refer to Appendix B). Factor analysis yielded three components (project team competence, rewards, and communication and change) and these were shown to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context.

The main intention of the study was to investigate the link between people-centred factors and ERP implementation project success. The three components of people-centred factors were found to predict significantly the ERP implementation project success. Project team competence, rewards, and communication and change accounted for 70 per cent of the variation of ERP system implementation project success. Therefore, the measures developed in this study could contribute to a better understanding of the people-centred factors for successful ERP system implementations in organizations. As we have not come across previous empirical studies that investigated in detail the links between people-centred factors and ERP system implementation project success, considerable research is necessary to validate the links suggested in this study to determine the impact of people-centred factors on ERP implementation project success. The current study represents a step in that direction.

The findings of the study provide some implications for ERP implementation projects. The measures developed in this study could contribute to a better

understanding of the ERP implementation project success and people-centred factors that influence ERP implementation project success. The findings established the requirement of sufficient skilled experts as project team members, who can build the relationship of trust among team members to ensure the success of the project (refer to Table 2). Further, the projects are more difficult to implement if project team members are reluctant to learn the new system, job functions and accept the new processes and procedures. Clear understanding and sharing of the goal, close personal communication among the team members, regular meetings, and honest and open information policy between the key parties also influence ERP project implementation success (refer to Table 2). Furthermore, the need of clear performance management measures, and the need of tangible as well as intangible reward system tied to ERP system implementation are also prominent from the findings (refer to Table 2). The identification of people-centred factors that influence ERP implementation project success becomes important as more and more organisations implement ERP systems and empirical research in this area is presently lacking.

Practitioners could use the measures proposed in this study as a diagnostic tool to assess and analyse issues in connection to ERP implementations to take necessary corrective actions to accomplish project success. In this regard, findings suggest that “people-centred factors” that influence ERP implementation project success is a multidimensional construct; one must not focus exclusively on any single factor. Practitioners or researchers can employ project team competence, rewards, and communication and change as measures to assess and analyse what aspects of people-centred issues are most problematical in their ERP system implementations. This will enhance the understanding of the extent of ERP implementation project success and how it has been influenced by people-centred factors. Once this understanding is gained, necessary actions could be taken to improve ERP system implementations.

7. Limitations and future research work

There are some limitations in this study. First, extant literature identifies ERP system implementation as a “triple play” that combines people, technology, and processes. However, the current study was confined to investigate people-centred factors. Therefore, future enquiries could extend beyond the people-centred factors to include technical and process-related aspects of ERP implementation. Second, the current study focused on a limited number of variables for ERP implementation project success and people-centred issues. Some other variables associated with ERP implementation, for example, the leadership style of project leaders may be added to improve the understanding of ERP implementation project success. Further, we used perceived measures to define ERP project implementation success. The actual data of success outcomes were left out due to the difficulty in securing the factual data from the participating organisations. This led us to another limitation of the study, i.e., a common method bias due to collecting data on the dependent variable and independent variables from the respondent. Further, data was collected from one of the randomly selected main persons who have been involved in the ERP implementation project as a project-team member in each firm. It would be an advantage if we could have collected data from several members in a project team. Furthermore, when respondents rate their implementation experiences on a Likert-scale, there could be situations where individuals consistently give higher (or middle) estimates for the ERP implementation project experiences that they have had. However, the validity of a measure cannot be truly established on the basis of a single cross-sectional study. The validation of a measure requires the assessment of measurement properties over a variety of samples in similar and different contexts. Hence, future research, in different samples and longitudinal studies, are necessary that compliment questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data. As an initial attempt, the study had not investigated culture-specific people-centred issues

that could influence ERP implementation project success. Future studies can incorporate such variables.

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Figures

Figure 1. Final research model

Note. **p<.01; ***p<.001

Tables

Table 1. Profile of the firms and respondents (N=74)

	%		%
<i>Industrial sector</i>		<i>Number of modules implemented</i>	
Manufacturing	35	Less than 5	41
Telecommunication	27	5 - 10	43
Trade and Logistics	11	More than 10	16
Hotels and Travel	8		
Diversified Holdings	7	<i>Frequently implemented modules</i>	
Power and Energy	7	Financial accounting	93
Financial services	5	Materials management	82
		Sales and distribution	73
		Maintenance	47
<i>Number of employees</i>		HR	39
More than 1001	45		
501-1000	27	<i>ERP use durations</i>	
201-500	24	Less than 3 years	59
50 -200	4	3 - 5 years	27
		More than 5 years	14
<i>ERP vendor</i>			
SAP	37	<i>Respondents' experience with ERP implementations</i>	
IFS	30	Less than 5 years	64
Oracle	14	5 -10 years	29
Other	19	More than 10 years	7
<i>Product type</i>			
Customized	69		
Off-the-shelf	31		

Table 2. Summarised results: factor analysis diagnostics

	Standardised regression estimate	P value	Standardised Cronbach's alpha
<i>ERP implementation project success</i>			.798
The project is completed within budget	.811	.001	
The project is completed within the scheduled time	.561	.004	
Clarity of the system	.675	.000	
Accuracy of the system	.919	.000	
Timeliness of the system	.841	.000	
Stability of the system	.583	.000	
Achievement of the business case	.701	.000	
Explained variation	67.3%		
Eigenvalue	4.47		
<i>Human resource factors</i>			
<i>Project team competence</i>			.913
Availability of sufficient expertise	.831	.000	
Skilled and competent project team members	.823	.000	
Composition of the project team	.862	.000	
Trust among team members	.717	.000	
Accept new processes and procedures	.769	.000	
Learn the new system and job functions	.676	.000	
Explained variation	33.21%		
Eigenvalue	8.51		
<i>Rewards</i>			.895
Rewards based on performance	.841	.000	
Recognition through tangible rewards	.825	.000	
Clarify future career opportunities	.684	.000	
Celebrate success	.789	.000	
Create a pleasant working environment	.811	.000	
Explained variation	28.43%		
Eigenvalue	6.30		
<i>Communication and change</i>			.884
Establish communication guidelines	.600	.000	
Regular open communication between key parties	.749	.000	
Identify sources of resistance	.880	.000	
Communicate the strategic vision of ERP	.686	.000	
Cooperation and involvement of key parties	.861	.000	
Explained variation	19.26%		
Eigenvalue	4.13		

Table 3. Descriptive statistics and zero-order correlations

Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3
1. ERP implementation project success	3.92	0.50	1		
2. Project team competence	3.89	0.83	.302	1	
3. Rewards	3.64	1.07	.441	.256	1
4. Communication and change	3.13	0.97	.332	.187	.168

Note. All correlations are significant at .01 level (2 tailed).

Table 4. Goodness-of-fit indices for the model

Fit indices	CMIN/df	GFI	RMSEA	PCLOSE	CFI	PRATIO
Outcome	1.29	0.86	0.04	0.85	0.94	0.82

Appendix A: ERP implementation success measures

Item	Author(s)	Al-Mashari et al. (2003)	Ang et al. (1994 and 2002)	Bailey and Pearson (1983)	Burns and Turnipseed (1991)	Delone and McLean (1992 and 2003)	Hong and Kim (2002)	Malbert et al. (2003)	Mandal and Gunasekaran (2002)	Markus et al. (2000)	Umble et al. (2003)	Wang et al. 2005	Wu and Wang (2007)	Yusuf et al. (2004)	Zhang et al. (2005)	
Accuracy						√										√
Clarity						√										
Content/content of the information system						√										
Flexibility				√												
Intended business performance improvement/achievement of predetermined corporate goals		√					√									√
On time		√					√									√
Reliability								√								√
System acceptance and usage			√													√
System stability																√
Timeliness/response time		√														√
User satisfaction		√														√
Within budget		√					√									√

Appendix B: People-centred factors that influence ERP implementation projects

Item	Author(s)	Bancroft et al. (1998)	Bingi et al. (1999)	Falkowski et al. (1998)	Holland and Light (1999)	King (2005)	Kraemer and et al. (2003)	Manthou et al. (1996)	Roberts and Barrar (1992)	Rosario (2000)	Somers and Nelson (2001)	Sum et al. (1997)	Sumner (1999)	Umble et al. (2003)	Wang et al. (2005)	
Change management programme and culture			√		√		√		√							√
Effective Communication				√						√						√
Monitoring and evaluating performance				√				√								√
Project team competence, composition and team work			√		√											√
Rewards/recognition		√														√
Roles of project team members and allocation of responsibility																√

Appendix C: Measures

ERP implementation project success measures

The project is completed within budget.

The project is completed within the scheduled time.

Clarity of the system

Accuracy of the system

Timeliness of the system

Stability of the system

Achievement of the business case

People-centred factors

Availability of sufficient expertise

Skilled and competent project team members

Composition of the project team

Trust among team members

Learning the new system and job functions

Accept new processes and procedures

Establish communication guidelines

Regular open communication between key parties

Identify sources of resistance

Communicate the strategic vision of ERP

Cooperation and involvement of key parties

Rewards based on performance

Recognition through tangible rewards

Clarify future career opportunities

Celebrate success

Create a pleasant working environment

Appendix D: Summary statistics of ERP implementation project success and Human resource aspects

	Mean	S.D.	Skewness
<i>ERP implementation project success</i>			
The project is completed within budget	3.25	1.06	1.01
The project is completed within the scheduled time	2.77	1.00	.47
Clarity of the system	3.86	.69	.57
Accuracy of the system	3.86	.75	-.98
Timeliness of the system	4.03	.74	-1.49
Stability of the system	3.94	.62	-1.02
Achievement of the business case	3.79	.76	-1.17
<i>Human resource factors</i>			
<i>Project team competence</i>			
Availability of sufficient expertise	3.62	1.06	.21
Skilled and competent project team members	3.72	.94	.18
Composition of the project team	3.56	.85	.27
Trust among team members	3.74	1.05	-.62
Accept new processes and procedures	3.60	.92	-.40
Learn the new system and job functions	3.46	1.14	.05
<i>Rewards</i>			
Rewards based on performance	2.66	1.15	-.90
Recognition through tangible rewards	2.76	1.30	-.28
Clarify future career opportunities	3.13	1.18	.06
Celebrate success	3.15	1.27	-.51
Create a pleasant working environment	3.38	1.03	.48
<i>Communication and change</i>			
Establish communication guidelines	3.08	1.01	.15
Regular open communication between key parties	2.96	1.05	-.31
Identify sources of resistance	3.25	1.03	.02
Communicate the strategic vision of ERP	2.86	1.05	-.11
Cooperation and involvement of key parties	3.46	.96	.19